

Proposal

LISS panel grant 2023

Cognitive strengths and deficits in adverse conditions: A balanced view

1 Layperson summary

The dominant view in the social sciences is that, on average, exposure to adversity impairs cognitive abilities, such as planning, goal-directed behavior, and self-control. This view, however, is incomplete: people might also develop intact, or even enhanced, abilities for solving challenges in adverse conditions. Understanding these abilities is critical to close achievement gaps in education and job contexts. Here, we will investigate the associations between two types of adversity—exposure to violence and poverty—and two cognitive abilities that are central to successful goal-directed behavior and self-control: switching attention and ignoring distractions. The central question is: to what extent does adversity impair/enhance abilities, and to what extent does it shape other processes—such as being more cautious? We will answer these questions using a well-developed analytic technique, Drift Diffusion Modeling. The results will have implications for fundamental science and can inform policy and interventions aimed at alleviating the negative impact of adversity.

2 Background of the study and relationship to the literature

Decades of research shows that adversity—defined here as prolonged exposure to and/or perception of poverty or environmental threat—tends to lower performance on a wide variety of cognitive tasks.¹ However, recent studies show that this deficit framework is incomplete: people might also develop enhanced abilities for solving challenges in high-adversity contexts². For example, recent studies suggest that growing up in a threatening environment enhances the ability to **shift attention** between tasks and **update working memory**—both of which are crucial for keeping track of the environment. However, we know little about why adversity affects distinct—but often related—abilities differently, and

how to best quantify an individual's exposure to adversity. Here, we investigate 1) which cognitive abilities are enhanced/impaired by adversity in a sample of 20-55 year-olds, and 2) whether cognitive abilities are shaped more strongly by subjective experiences or objective levels of adversity.

Measuring abilities

Amidst decades of research supporting deficit frameworks (i.e., adversity impairing cognitive abilities), recent studies have found a comparatively small set of abilities that may be enhanced by adversity. However, using standard analysis strategies, it is easy to overestimate deficits and underestimate enhancements, as abilities can become confounded with other processes that influence performance. Specifically:

1. **Lowered performance does not necessarily indicate impaired cognition.** There can be different reasons for lowered performance. For example, people might be slower out of caution (e.g., due to performance anxiety) or be slower to execute their decision. Commonly used measures (such as mean response times) are unable to distinguish between these processes. Therefore, we risk inferring cognitive deficits where there are none.
2. **Task-general impairments may obscure task-specific enhanced abilities.** Task-general processes are processes that are shared between many cognitive tasks, such as general processing speed. Task-specific abilities are abilities unique to a particular cognitive measure (e.g., inhibition). Adversity may impair task-general processes (causing slower overall responses) while separately shaping specific abilities. If so, studies analyzing performance on a single task may incorrectly interpret lower general processing speed as a deficit in a specific cognitive ability.

We will tease apart the cognitive processes shaped by adversity.

Measuring adversity

A major debate in the literature concerns how to measure adversity⁴. Researchers often measure **subjective perceptions** of adversity, but these do not accurately reflect **objective levels** of adversity (e.g., self-reported vs. actual neighborhood crime rates)⁵. Are cognitive abilities more strongly associated with objective markers or with perceived experience of the environment? We will use CBS microdata to compare objective governmental data with self-reported experiences.

Current study

We will measure two important cognitive abilities: switching attention between different goals (**attention shifting**) and ignoring distractions (**inhibition**). Previous research suggests that adversity enhances attention shifting but impairs inhibition. We will include multiple measures of each ability to tease apart task-specific and task-general processes.

We include 1) existing LISS measures of adversity and 2) new measures of childhood and current exposure to violence and poverty (as the effects of adversity might be different at different stages of development). Through CBS data, we will also obtain objective markers of people's environments to

determine whether they are more strongly related with cognitive abilities than subjective experiences of adversity.

Originality

1. There are almost no existing datasets well-suited for separating the different processes that might be affected by adversity. Our task battery is specifically tailored to achieve this goal.
2. We will enrich LISS with measures capturing childhood and current exposure to neighborhood violence and poverty.
3. CBS microdata will afford a unique assessment of objective adversity levels in people's environment over time.

3 Research questions

Our research will focus on five interrelated research questions:

RQ 1: What is the association between childhood adversity and task-general speed of processing? *We expect the association to be negative.*

RQ 2: How is childhood adversity associated with attention-shifting and inhibition abilities after accounting for task-general speed of processing? *We expect the association with inhibition to be negative, but the association with attention-shifting to be positive.*

RQ 3: Are different types of childhood adversity associated differently with task-general and task-specific processes? *We expect stronger deficits for poverty than for violence exposure. We expect violence exposure to be positively associated with attention shifting ability.*

RQ4: Are childhood levels of adversity and current levels of adversity differently associated with task-general and task-specific processes? *We do not have specific predictions, as relatively little is known about the importance of the timing of adversity on cognitive outcomes.*

RQ5: Are subjective and objective indicators of adversity differently associated with task-specific abilities and task-general processes? *We do not have specific predictions, as this has not been investigated by previous literature.*

4 Methodological approach

Requested sample size

A power analysis⁶ indicated that with an alpha of $\alpha = 0.05$, we will have > 90% power to detect small effect sizes ($\beta = 0.1$) with a sample size ranging between $N = 730$ and $N = 980$ when the reliability of the measures is at least moderate (0.6 – 0.7). Therefore, we request a total sample size of $N = 1,000$.

Sample composition

1. Participants between 20-55 years old;

2. Permission for CBS linkage.

Cognitive Tasks

We will include a total of six cognitive tasks spanning three domains: 1) attention shifting, 2) inhibition, and 3) basic processing speed. See section 6 for visualizations of all tasks.

1. *Attention Shifting.* Switching Task, Number-Letter Task, and Global-Local Task.
2. *Inhibition.* Flanker Task and Anti-saccade Task.
3. *Processing Speed.* Posner Task.

Survey measures

We will measure two types of adversity—violence exposure and poverty—using a combination of measures from the LISS data archive and new measures. We focus on these types of adversity because they have been associated with both cognitive deficits and enhancements in prior research. **We will treat adversity as a continuous variable.** See section 6 for an overview of the new measures.

1. *Violence Exposure.*
 - a) Measured in study: *Neighborhood Violence Scale* (current exposure and exposure < age 18)
 - b) LISS data archive: *Conventional crime victimization* (data from six waves).
2. *Poverty*
 - a) Measured in study: *Material Needs Scale* (current exposure and exposure < age 18)
 - b) LISS data archive: Mean level and variability in income over time, adjusted for family size (from *background variables*).

Estimated based on existing data, the cognitive tasks will take ~24 minutes, and the surveys ~4 minutes.

Linking with CBS data

We will use CBS microdata in two ways. First, the CBS RINPERSOONS identifier allows us to look up where participants have lived over the last years. CBS grants us access at the zipcode-4 level. With this information, we can retrieve publicly available CBS data—such as police reports, crime rates, average neighborhood housing prices, and neighborhood green spaces—to quantify aspects of participants' environment over time. We can combine these *objective* measures of violence exposure, neighborhood wealth, and neighborhood deprivation with the *subjective* measures derived from LISS surveys. This allows us to compare their association with cognitive functioning, as well as the correlation between these measures. Second, we plan to use specific CBS microdata related to health to enrich measures from the LISS panel (measured in *Health*). Specifically, we can explore the association between objective measures, such as money spent on health insurance, to subjective, self-reported health. We can then explore to what extent objective and subjective measures of health moderate the relationship between adversity and cognitive functioning. We are currently considering the following population-level microdata, but we are also open to advice and suggestions from ODISSEI and SODA: prescribed

medication; mental health care trajectory; healthcare insurance not paid for six months; reimbursed healthcare costs.

Analysis approach

1. For each cognitive task, we will first use **Drift Diffusion Modeling** to translate raw performance (i.e., response time and accuracy) into distinct underlying cognitive processes. *This allows us to distinguish between task-relevant cognitive abilities and task-irrelevant processes (e.g., levels of response caution, speed at which participants execute the response).*
2. Next, we use structural equation modeling to estimate **task-general processes** (i.e., processes shared across all tasks) and **task-specific abilities**. We then analyze the association between different types of adversity and task-specific and task-general processes.

Figure 1. Overview of the analysis approach. Dashed arrows represent regression paths.

5 Implications for research, practice and/or society

Our study addresses a major debate in contemporary developmental science: How does adversity shape cognition? This debate is occurring across subfields, including (but not limited to) executive functioning, social cognition, language, and emotion. The debate is essential to basic and applied science. Globally, hundreds of millions of people experience adversity. How are their minds affected? Which developmental processes are involved? The proposed study is theoretically groundbreaking because it has the potential to overturn the dominant ideas in the field about which types of adversity influence cognition, and how these adversities shape abilities vs. processes that do not reflect ability.

These findings have real-world consequences. First, the framing of cognitive differences resulting from adverse experiences can affect people's self-views and/or create negative feedback loops with educators,

employers, and policy makers. Overall, a deficit framing reinforces and perpetuates the stigma associated with living in adversity. Second, the way we interpret performance differences has important implications for interventions that aim to bridge performance gaps. Should such interventions focus on cognitive training? Or should they try to align cognitive tasks more closely with people's lived experience, for example, by making their content more ecologically relevant? The answers to these questions depend largely on our understanding of which processes and abilities are affected by adversity.

Beyond our specific research aims, enriching the LISS data archive with cognitive tasks is relevant for many other researchers with different research topics. For example, the cognitive data could be used as moderators or mediators in studies focusing on other measures already present in LISS, such as of personality, work, and alcohol and drug use. Besides the current study measuring attention shifting and inhibition, we will conduct a LISS study in October 2023 measuring aspects of working memory. Combining these two studies, we will have covered the three domains commonly seen as central to executive functioning—inhibition, attention shifting, and working memory updating. We are thrilled that other researchers will be freely able to use these cognitive data to address a wide range of research questions.

References

- 1 Sheridan, et al. (2022). *Science Advances*. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abn4316>
- 2 Frankenhuis, et al. (2020). *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2020.03.037>
3. Vermeent, et al. (Registered Report: Accepted protocol). *Developmental Science*.
4. Sheridan, et al. (2014). *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2014.09.001>
5. Ambrey et al. (2014). *Social Indicators Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-013-0521-6>
6. Kretschmar et al. (2019). *Journal of Research in Personality*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2019.03.007>

6 Preliminary content of the LISS panel survey questions (optional)

Survey items

All items are answered using the following response categories:

1. Helemaal mee oneens
2. Mee oneens
3. Deels mee oneens
4. Niet mee eens, niet mee oneens
5. Deels mee eens
6. Mee eens
7. Helemaal mee eens

Past violence exposure (<17 years old)

*"Voor de volgende vragen zijn we geïnteresseerd in uw jeugd jaren van **vóór de leeftijd van 17 jaar**. In hoeverre bent u het oneens of oneens met de onderstaande uitspraken?"*

VP1 Ik ben opgegroeid in een veilige buurt (R)

VP2 Criminaliteit kwam regelmatig voor in de buurt waar ik woonde

VP3 Ik ben opgegroeid in een rijke buurt (R)

VP4 Fysieke gevechten waren gebruikelijk in de buurt waar ik opgroeide

VP5 Schiet- of steekpartijen (met wapens, zoals messen of pistolen) kwamen voor in de buurt waarin ik opgroeide

VP6 In de buurt waar ik opgroeide, voelden de meeste mensen zich onveilig wanneer zij in het donker allen over straat liepen

VP7 In de buurt waar ik opgroeide, was het belangrijk dat je in staat was jezelf fysiek te verdedigen tegen anderen.

Past poverty (<17 years old)

*"Voor de volgende vragen zijn we geïnteresseerd in uw jeugd jaren van **vóór de leeftijd van 17 jaar**."*

PP1 Mijn gezin had genoeg geld om de woning te kunnen huren of kopen die we nodig hadden (R)

PP2 Mijn gezin had genoeg geld om de kleding te kunnen kopen die we nodig hadden (R)

PP3 Mijn gezin had genoeg geld om het voedsel te kunnen kopen dat we nodig hadden (R)

PP4 Mijn gezin had genoeg geld om de medische zorg (bijv: dokter bezoeken, medicijnen kopen) te kunnen betalen die we nodig hadden. (R)

Current violence exposure

*"Voor de volgende vragen zijn we geïnteresseerd in uw ervaringen **op dit moment** in uw leven. In hoeverre bent u het oneens of oneens met de onderstaande uitspraken?"*

VC1 Ik woon in een veilige buurt (R)

VC2 Criminaliteit komt regelmatig voor in de buurt waarin ik woon

VC3 Ik woon in een rijke buurt (R)

VC4 Fysieke gevechten zijn gebruikelijk in de buurt waarin ik woon

VC5 Schiet-of steekpartijen (met wapens, zoals messen of pistolen) komen voor in de buurt waarin ik woon

VC6 In de buurt waarin ik woon, voelen de meeste mensen zich onveilig wanneer zij in het donker alleen over straat lopen

VC7 In de buurt waarin ik woon, is het belangrijk dat je in staat bent jezelf fysiek te verdedigen tegen anderen.

Current poverty

PC1 Ik heb genoeg geld om de woning te kunnen huren of kopen die ik nodig heb (R)

PC2 Ik heb genoeg geld om de kleding te kunnen kopen die ik nodig heb (R)

PC3 Ik heb genoeg geld om het voedsel te kunnen kopen dat ik nodig heb (R)

PC4 Ik heb genoeg geld om de medische zorg (bijv. dokter bezoeken, medicijnen kopen) te kunnen betalen die ik nodig heb (R)

Cognitive measures

INHIBITION – Flanker Task

INHIBITION – Antisaccade Task

ATTENTION SHIFTING – Switching Task

ATTENTION SHIFTING – Letter-Number Task

ATTENTION SHIFTING – Switching Task

BASIC PROCESSING SPEED – Posner Task

